

USE OF SMA TO INDUCE SNAP-THROUGH OF UNSYMMETRIC LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A theory is developed and experiments designed to study the feasibility of using shape memory alloy (SMA) wires to effect the snap through of unsymmetric composite laminates. The concept is presented in the context of structural morphing, that is, a structure changing shape to adjust to changing conditions or to change operating characteristics. While the specific problem studied is a simplification, the overall concept is to potentially take advantage of structures which have multiple equilibrium configurations and expend power only to change the structure from one configuration to another rather than to continuously expend power to hold the structure in the changed configuration. The unsymmetric laminate could be the structure itself, or simply part of a structure. Specifically, a theory is presented which allows for the prediction of the moment levels needed to effect the snap-through event. The moment is generated by a force and support arrangement attached to the laminate. A heated SMA wire attached to the supports provides the force. The necessary SMA constitutive behavior and laminate mechanics are presented. To avoid dealing with the heat transfer aspects of the SMA wire, the theory is used to predict snap through as a function of SMA wire temperature, which can be measured directly. The geometry and force level considerations of the experiment are discussed, and the results of testing four unsymmetric laminates are compared with predictions. Laminate strain levels vs. temperature and the snap-through temperatures are measured for these laminates. Repeatability of the experimental results is generally good, and the predictions are in reasonable agreement with the measurements.

KEYWORDS: Unsymmetric laminates, shape-memory alloys, snap-through, instability, modelling.

INTRODUCTION AND BACKGROUND

Unsymmetrical laminates provide interesting characteristics for discussions regarding multiple equilibrium configurations, structural stability, and the ability to design shape into a structure. For example, a $[90_4/0_4]_T$ laminate that is flat at its elevated cure temperature, as in fig. 1a, cools from its cure temperature to have two equilibrium configurations. One configuration is cylindrical and has a large curvature in the x -direction and an imperceptible curvature in the y -direction, fig. 1b. The other configuration is cylindrical and has a large curvature in the y -direction and an imperceptible curvature in the x -direction, fig. 1c. The curvatures for the two configurations are equal but of opposite signs, and the laminate can be changed from one configuration to the other by a simple snap-through action initiated by applying equal and opposite moments to the edges of the laminate. Analysis indicates there is a third equilibrium configuration that is saddle-shaped, as in fig. 1d. A stability investigation indicates the saddle is not stable, while both of the cylindrical configurations are stable. A $[-60_4/30_4]_T$ laminate will have similar characteristics. However,

because of the off-axis nature of the fiber orientations, the cooled laminate will have twist curvature, and the principal curvature directions will not be aligned with the x - and y -coordinate axes. While these characteristics of unsymmetrically laminated composite materials are quite interesting, modeling can become involved and traditional analysis methods, like finite-element analysis, have difficulty with the multiple equilibrium configurations and the inherent instability in the problem. Dano and Hyer [1] expanded on the earlier work of Hyer [2] to study several families of unsymmetric laminates both experimentally and with a semi-closed form energy-based Rayleigh-Ritz predictive technique. Schlecht and Schulte [3] used finite-elements to study unsymmetric laminates. Others have also investigated their behavior, namely, Jun and Hong [4], Peeters, et al [5], and Cho, et al [6].

Fig. 1. Shapes of a $[90_4/0_4]_T$ laminate

The idea of being able to apply moments to the laminate and change the laminate to a significantly different equilibrium configuration is intriguing. In the areas of structural morphing and so-called smart structures, actuators are used to force a structure from one configuration to another to react to the environment or to change the operating characteristics of the structure. However, most smart structure concepts require the continuous application of a force, at the expense of a continuous source of energy, to cause a structure to maintain a changed configuration. With the use of unsymmetric laminates, it might be possible to use the multiple equilibrium configurations to advantage. The unsymmetric laminate could be the structure itself, or it could be part of a structure, and energy would be expended only to change the structure from one configuration to the other. A continuous supply of energy would not be required.

This paper explores the notion of using shape memory alloy (SMA) wires to effect the snap-through from one stable configuration to the other. The concept to be discussed is illustrated in fig. 2. There a $[-60_4/30_4]_T$ laminate is shown outfitted with supports of length e . A SMA wire is stretched between the tips of the supports. The wire has been pre-strained and is in the martensite phase. The wire is then heated and is

transformed to the austenite phase, whereupon it has the tendency to return to its initial length, and does so by generating enough force to pull the tips of the supports towards each other, thereby creating the equal and opposite moments needed to cause the laminate to snap. As the laminate deforms toward the snapping condition, the tips of the supports move due to the translations and rotations of the laminate at the base of the supports, but the line of action of the force is always directed along the line connecting the tips. The supports are mounted so that, initially, the line of action between the supports, denoted as the l -axis in fig. 2, is along the principal curvature direction. As the laminate deforms, however, the line of action changes. Of course, to effect the reverse snap, a similar arrangement of supports and SMA wire would be needed on the underside of the laminates.

Fig. 2. Geometry of SMA wire and support configuration for $[-60_4/30_4]_T$ laminate

The basic objective of the study was to be able to predict the deformation of the laminate, and in particular, the snap-through event, as a function of the temperature of the SMA wire. The wire was heated by passing current through it, and the concerns for voltage and current levels needed, heat transfer effects, etc. were not addressed. In the sections to follow, the method of predicting the deformation of an unsymmetric laminate to forces in the arrangement shown in fig. 2 is outlined. This has been discussed in Dano and Hyer [7] but, for purposes of completeness, it is briefly reviewed. Following that, the SMA governing equations are presented. The equations governing laminate behavior are then coupled to the SMA governing equations and the computation scheme to predict laminate shape as function of wire temperature is outlined. Experiments are then described to examine the deformation and snap-through characteristics of four unsymmetric laminates. The outcome of the experiments and the predictions of the computational scheme are compared.

REVIEW OF THEORY TO PREDICT SNAP-THROUGH FORCES

A planform view of the geometry locating the base of the supports is shown in fig. 3a. The angle Φ_o is the angle the principal curvature direction makes with the $+x$ -axis of the laminate before any forces are applied. The geometric quantities in fig. 3a are related by $x_s = L_s \cos \Phi_o$ and $y_s = L_s \sin \Phi_o$ where L_s , x_s , and y_s are measured when the laminate is flat. The response of the laminate to the SMA-induced forces is determined using the principle of virtual work, which can be stated as

$$\delta W_T = \delta \Pi - \delta W_F = 0, \quad (1)$$

where δW_T is the total virtual work, $\delta \Pi$ the first variation of the strain energy, and δW_F the virtual work of the applied forces. Assuming classical lamination theory is valid, the strain energy of the laminate, Π , can be expressed as a function of the material and geometric properties of the laminate, the temperature change of the laminate relative to the cure temperature, ΔT , and the total strains by,

$$\Pi = \int_{-\frac{L_x}{2}}^{\frac{L_x}{2}} \int_{-\frac{L_y}{2}}^{\frac{L_y}{2}} \int_{-\frac{H}{2}}^{\frac{H}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{11} \varepsilon_x^2 + \bar{Q}_{12} \varepsilon_x \varepsilon_y + \bar{Q}_{16} \gamma_{xy} \varepsilon_x + \frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{22} \varepsilon_y^2 + \bar{Q}_{26} \gamma_{xy} \varepsilon_y + \frac{1}{2} \bar{Q}_{66} \gamma_{xy}^2 \right. \\ \left. - \frac{L_x - L_y - H}{2} (\bar{Q}_{11} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{12} \alpha_y + \bar{Q}_{16} \alpha_{xy}) \varepsilon_x \Delta T - (\bar{Q}_{12} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{22} \alpha_y + \bar{Q}_{26} \alpha_{xy}) \varepsilon_y \Delta T + \right. \\ \left. - (\bar{Q}_{12} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{22} \alpha_y + \bar{Q}_{26} \alpha_{xy}) \varepsilon_y \Delta T - (\bar{Q}_{16} \alpha_x + \bar{Q}_{26} \alpha_y + \bar{Q}_{66} \alpha_{xy}) \gamma_{xy} \Delta T \right) dx dy dz \quad (2)$$

where the \bar{Q}_{ij} s are the transformed reduced stiffnesses of the individual layers, L_x and L_y are the planform dimensions of the laminate when it is flat, and H is the laminate thickness. The total strains ε_x , ε_y , γ_{xy} are given by the Kirchhoff hypothesis as

$$\varepsilon_x = \frac{\partial u^o}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w^o}{\partial x} \right)^2 - z \frac{\partial^2 w^o}{\partial x^2} \quad \varepsilon_y = \frac{\partial v^o}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w^o}{\partial y} \right)^2 - z \frac{\partial^2 w^o}{\partial y^2} \quad \gamma_{xy} = \frac{\partial u^o}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^o}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w^o}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w^o}{\partial y} - z \frac{\partial^2 w^o}{\partial x \partial y} \quad (3)$$

where u^o , v^o , and w^o are the displacement components in the x -, y - and z -directions, respectively. The displacements can be assumed to be of the form

$$u^o(x, y) = c_1 x + c_{12} y + \frac{1}{2} \left(c_4 - \frac{1}{2} c_9 c_{11} \right) x^2 y + \left(c_3 - \frac{c_{11}^2}{8} \right) x y^2 + \frac{1}{3} \left(c_2 - \frac{1}{2} c_9^2 \right) x^3 + \frac{1}{3} c_{13} y^3 \\ v^o(x, y) = c_{12} x + c_5 y + \left(c_6 - \frac{c_{11}^2}{8} \right) x^2 y + \frac{1}{2} \left(c_8 - \frac{1}{2} c_{10} c_{11} \right) x y^2 + \frac{1}{3} \left(c_7 - \frac{1}{2} c_{10}^2 \right) y^3 + \frac{1}{3} c_{14} x^3 \quad (4) \\ w^o(x, y) = \frac{1}{2} (c_9 x^2 + c_{10} y^2 + c_{11} xy),$$

where the $c_i, i=1,14$ are constants to be determined. Substituting eqs. 3 and 4 into eq. 2 results in an expression for the strain energy of the laminate of the form

$$\Pi = \Pi(c_i, i=1,14). \quad (5)$$

Fig. 3. Geometry of the force configuration

Obviously, Π is also a function of the laminate material properties, geometry, and temperature change, but here interest centers on its dependence on the unknown coefficients. From eq. 5, the first variation of the strain energy can be expressed as

$$\delta\Pi = \delta\Pi(c_1, c_2, \dots, \delta c_1, \delta c_2, \dots). \quad (6)$$

Referring to fig. 3b, the virtual work of the applied force F is defined as the work done by the force as the laminate is given a virtual displacement, that is,

$$\delta W_F = \vec{F} \cdot \delta \vec{R}_F \Big|_{\substack{x = x_s \\ y = y_s}} + \vec{F} \cdot \delta \vec{R}_F \Big|_{\substack{x = -x_s \\ y = -y_s}}. \quad (7)$$

The virtual displacement $\delta \vec{R}_F$ is evaluated by first computing the position vector \vec{R}_F of the force, relative to the origin of the coordinate system, and then taking its variation. As illustrated in fig. 3b, the position vector \vec{R}_F can be expressed as the sum of the position vector to the base of the support, \vec{r} , and the vector directed from the base of the support to the tip of the support, \vec{n}^* , i. e., $\vec{R}_F = \vec{r} + \vec{n}^*$. The vector \vec{r} can be written as

$$\vec{r} = (x + u^o(x, y, c_i, i=1,14))\vec{i} + (y + v^o(x, y, c_i, i=1,14))\vec{j} + w^o(x, y, c_i, i=1,14)\vec{k}, \quad (8)$$

where the notation is to emphasize the fact that the vector \vec{r} depends on the unknown coefficients as well as x and y . Since the vector \vec{n}^* is normal to the surface, it can be expressed as $\vec{n}^* = (e + H/2)\vec{n}$, where \vec{n} is the unit vector normal to the laminate surface at the support locations and $(e + H/2)$ is the distance from the laminate reference surface to the tip of the support. By definition, the unit vector \vec{n} at a point (x, y) on the laminate surface is given by,

$$\vec{n}(x, y) = \frac{\frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial x} \times \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial y}}{\left| \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial x} \times \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial y} \right|} = \frac{\vec{CP}}{|\vec{CP}|}. \quad (9)$$

Because of eq. 8, \vec{n} is a function of the $c_i, i=1,14$. The virtual displacement $\delta \vec{R}_F$ is given by

$$\delta \vec{R}_F = \delta \vec{r} + \delta \vec{n}^* = \sum_{i=1}^{14} \frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial c_i} \delta c_i + (e + H/2) \delta \vec{n} \quad (10)$$

From eq. 9, since \vec{r} is a function of the c_i , $\delta \vec{n}$ is of the form

$$\delta \vec{n} = \sum_{i=1}^{14} \vec{N}_i \delta c_i, \quad (11)$$

where \vec{N}_i is introduced as shorthand. As a result, using eqs. 10 and 11, $\delta \vec{R}_F$ can be written as

$$\delta \vec{R}_F = \sum_{i=1}^{14} \left(\frac{\partial \vec{r}}{\partial c_i} + \left(e + \frac{H}{2} \right) \vec{N}_i \right) \delta c_i. \quad (12)$$

The applied force \vec{F} can be expressed in terms of its components in the x - y - z coordinate system by

$$\vec{F} \Big|_{\substack{x = x_s \\ y = y_s}} = (-F \cos \beta)\vec{i} + (-F \sin \beta)\vec{j} \quad \vec{F} \Big|_{\substack{x = -x_s \\ y = -y_s}} = (F \cos \beta)\vec{i} + (F \sin \beta)\vec{j}, \quad (13)$$

where $\cos \beta$ and $\sin \beta$ can be evaluated using the expression for \vec{R}_F . Specifically, letting \vec{e}_l define the unit vector along the l -axis, then \vec{e}_l can be expressed as a function of \vec{R}_F by

$$\hat{e}_l = \frac{\vec{R}_F(x_s, y_s) - \vec{R}_F(-x_s, -y_s)}{|\vec{R}_F(x_s, y_s) - \vec{R}_F(-x_s, -y_s)|} = \cos\beta \hat{i} + \sin\beta \hat{j}, \quad (14)$$

where the vector defined by $\vec{R}_F(x_s, y_s) - \vec{R}_F(-x_s, -y_s)$ represents the vector pointing from the tip of the support at $(-x_s, -y_s)$ to the tip of support at (x_s, y_s) . The expressions for $\cos\beta$ and $\sin\beta$ needed in eq. 13 can then be deduced from eq. 14. Equations 12, 13, and 14 can be used to construct δW_F as a function of δc_i . With that, the expression for the total virtual work, is given by

$$\delta W_T = \sum_{i=1}^{14} \frac{\delta \Pi}{\delta c_i} \delta c_i - \delta W_F = \sum_{i=1}^{14} f_i \delta c_i. \quad (15)$$

The laminate is in equilibrium if the total virtual work vanishes, i.e., $\delta W_T=0$, for every admissible virtual displacement δc_i , $i=1,14$. Equating δW_T to zero requires

$$f_i = 0, \quad i=1,14. \quad (16)$$

By setting the temperature change ΔT equal to -280°F and the force F to zero, solving the equilibrium equations expressed by eq. 16 gives the cured shapes of the laminate at room temperature, as shown in fig. 1. By increasing F and keeping ΔT at -280°F , the solutions of the equilibrium equations give the configurations of the laminate as it is deformed by the force F at room temperature. In the computation of the equilibrium solution using the Newton-Raphson technique, the Jacobian

$$J = \left[\frac{\partial f_i}{\partial c_j} \right] \quad i, j=1,14 \quad (17)$$

is computed for each temperature increment. The equilibrium solution is stable if and only if the matrix J is positive definite.

USE OF SMA TO GENERATE FORCES

Since the objective here is to predict the snap-through event of the laminate as a function of the temperature of the SMA wire used to generate the force, a model is needed that relates the wire temperature to the force level generated. This is accomplished here by using a constitutive model for SMA wire developed by Boyd and Lagoudas [8]. The constitutive law is a simple generalized Hooke's law,

$$\sigma = E \varepsilon^e = E(\varepsilon - \varepsilon^t - \alpha(T - T_o)) \quad , \quad (18)$$

where, σ , ε^e , ε , and ε^t are the uniaxial stress, elastic strain, total strain, and transformation strain, respectively. T and T_o are, respectively, the present and reference temperature. The extensional modulus E and the thermal expansion coefficient α of the SMA wire are both dependent on the martensite volume fraction ξ , and are assumed to be equal to $E_A + \xi(E_M - E_A)$ and $\alpha_A + \xi(\alpha_M - \alpha_A)$, respectively. E_A , α_A and E_M , α_M are the properties of the SMA in, respectively, a pure austenitic (A) and pure martensitic (M) phase. The transformation strain ε^t is directly related to the martensite volume fraction by

$$\varepsilon^t = \varepsilon_o \xi, \quad (19)$$

ε_o being the initial plastic strain in the SMA wire. At $\xi=1$ the SMA wire is fully martensitic and the transformation strain is equal to the initial strain ε_o . As transformation from the martensitic to the austenitic phases occurs, the initial strain is recovered and therefore strain ε^t decreases. The constitutive equation, eq. 18, is used in parallel with a kinetic equation governing the phase transformation which has been derived by using the first and second law of thermodynamics. This kinetic equation can be expressed as

$$\Psi = \sigma^{eff} \varepsilon_o + \frac{1}{2} \Delta a^1 \sigma^2 + \Delta \alpha \sigma (T - T_o) + \rho \Delta a^4 T - \frac{\partial f(\xi)}{\partial \xi} - Y = 0, \quad (20)$$

where ρ is the SMA density, $\Delta a^1 = 1/E_M - 1/E_A$, $\Delta \alpha = \alpha_M - \alpha_A$, $\sigma^{eff} = \sigma - \rho b_2 \varepsilon^t$, b_2 being the kinetic hardening parameter, $\rho \Delta a^4$ is the difference of the entropy between the martensite and the austenite phases at the reference state, Y is the threshold value of transformation, $f(\xi) = (1/2) \rho b_1 \xi^2$, b_1 being the isotropic hardening parameter. Parameter b_2 is assumed to be zero. Parameters $\rho \Delta a^4$, Y , and b_1 take different values. For a martensite-to-austenite transformation, $\rho \Delta a^4 = -C_A \varepsilon_o$, $Y = -C_A \varepsilon_o A_{fo}$, and $b_1 = (1/\rho) C_A \varepsilon_o (A_{fo} - A_{so})$. For an austenite-to-martensite transformation, $\rho \Delta a^4 = -C_M \varepsilon_o$, $Y = -C_M \varepsilon_o M_{so}$, and $b_1 = (1/\rho) C_M \varepsilon_o (M_{so} - M_{fo})$. In the above expressions M_{so} , A_{so} , M_{fo} , and A_{fo} are the start and finish temperatures at zero stress for, respectively, the martensitic and the austenitic transformation. The parameters C_A and C_M are the slopes of the relations between the so-called critical stress and temperature. Substituting eqs. 18 and 19 into eq. 20 leads to a non-linear algebraic equation expressed in terms of variables ε , T , and ξ , namely,

$$\Psi = \Psi(\varepsilon, T, \xi) = 0. \quad (21)$$

The thermomechanical response of the SMA wire can be characterized by solving eq. 21. It is through the strain in eq. 21, and also the stress by virtue of eq. 18, that the mechanics of the unsymmetric laminate enter. Essentially, the thermomechanical behavior of the wire and the mechanics of the unsymmetric laminate are coupled through the movement of the supports and the force in the supports - i.e. strain in the wire and the stress in the wire. In terms of previously defined variables, the stress and total strain in the wire are given by

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A_{SMA}} \quad \varepsilon = \varepsilon_o + \frac{\Delta L_{SMA}}{L_{SMA}^o} = \varepsilon_o + \left(\frac{|\vec{R}_F(x_s, y_s) - \vec{R}_F(-x_s, -y_s)|}{|\vec{R}_F(x_s, y_s) - \vec{R}_F(-x_s, -y_s)|_{F=0}} - 1 \right), \quad (22)$$

where A_{SMA} is the SMA wire cross section area, and ΔL_{SMA} and L_{SMA}^o are, respectively, the change in length and the initial length of the SMA wire.

The deformations of the laminate can be predicted as a function of the temperature in the SMA wire by solving the above set of equations in conjunction with eq. 16, which governs the laminate behavior. When the SMA wire is heated above the austenite start temperature, the wire starts to contract, stress is generated in the wire, which results in applying a force F on the laminate. The force F is induced by the phase transformation and is therefore not known in advance. The equations were solved by assuming values for the force F generated by the SMA wire and using the governing equations for the laminate and the SMA wire to compute the corresponding plate response, strain in the wire, martensite volume fraction, and temperature in the wire. For the calculations, the properties of the SMA wire are taken to be

$$\begin{array}{lll} E_A = 9,710 \text{ Ksi} & C_A = 1.104 \text{ Ksi}/^\circ\text{F} & \varepsilon_{omax} = 8\% \\ E_M = 3,810 \text{ Ksi} & A_{so} = 94.3 \text{ }^\circ\text{F} & \varepsilon_o = 5\% \\ a_A = 19.8 \times 10^{-6} /^\circ\text{F} & A_{fo} = 120.2 \text{ }^\circ\text{F} & A_{SMA} = (\pi d^2)/4 \\ a_M = 11.88 \times 10^{-6} /^\circ\text{F} & & d = 20 \times 10^{-3} \text{ in.} \end{array} \quad (23)$$

The properties of the composite material are equal to

$$\begin{array}{lll} E_1 = 24,8 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & E_2 = 1,270 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} & G_{12} = 1,030 \times 10^6 \text{ psi} \\ \nu_{12} = 0,335 & \alpha_1 = 0,345 \times 10^{-6} /^\circ\text{F} & \alpha_2 = 15,34 \times 10^{-6} /^\circ\text{F}. \end{array} \quad (24)$$

COMPARISON OF NUMERICAL RESULTS WITH EXPERIMENTS

When using SMA wire with highly curved unsymmetric laminates, several important issues have to be considered. First, the SMA wire should be attached on the laminate close enough to its surface so that the recovery strain does not exceed the maximum recovery strain, which, as stated in eq. 22, is 8% for the material used here. However, the supports should be long enough so that the wire does not touch the laminate. Since the $[90_4/0_4]_T$ laminate exhibits the largest curvature, this laminate will require the largest SMA strain recovery when compared to the other laminates. Therefore, the $[90_4/0_4]_T$ laminate is a good case for determining the design of the wire support geometry. The geometric parameters of the supports, L_s and e , were chosen to be equal to 4.0 in and 0.625 in, respectively.

The second issue to consider is the force level necessary for snapping. However, if one wire can not generate enough force, several wires can be used in parallel. The key is to determine for each laminate the number of wires that must be used. It was decided to use four parallel wires for the $[90_4/0_4]_T$, the $[-30_4/30_4]_T$ and the $[-60_4/30_4]_T$ laminates. Since the $[60_4/30_4]_T$ laminate requires a smaller snapping force [7], just two wires were used. Though the geometry of the two and four length arrangements did not exactly coincide with the geometry of the single force and two supports shown in figs. 2 and 3, and assumed in the subsequent theory developed, the net effects of the multiple lengths of wire were felt to be a reasonable approximation to the effects of a single wire.

Tests were conducted on four unsymmetric laminates with stacking sequences $[-30_4/30_4]_T$, $[-60_4/30_4]_T$, $[60_4/30_4]_T$ and $[90_4/0_4]_T$. The dimensions of the laminates were as in fig. 2, namely, $L_x=L_y=11.5$ in and $H=0.04$ in. Back-to-back 0-45-90 strain gage rosettes were used to measure the strain response of the laminates as a function of the temperature in the SMA wire. Ideally, the displacements or curvatures of the laminate as a function of wire temperature would have been measured. These responses, however, are difficult to measure because of the large displacements involved. The strain response was easier to measure and was used as an indicator of laminate response. For each unsymmetric laminate the tests were conducted twice. In the figures to follow, the relationship between the SMA wire temperature and the measured and predicted strains is plotted for the $[-30_4/30_4]_T$ laminate.

As can be observed in fig. 4, for both test 1 and test 2, the measured strains for the $[-30_4/30_4]_T$ laminate changed very slowly, or not at all, as the SMA wire was first heated above the room temperature start condition. The predictions also indicated a slow change. As the SMA wire was further heated, the rate of change of the measured strains with increasing temperature remained slow for both tests, while the predictions indicated that the strains should change more rapidly. At a temperature of 104° F for test 1, the laminate snapped, as characterized by a sudden jump in the strains. The strain along the 45° -axis, ϵ_{45} , changed the most before the snap-through because, compared to the x - and y -axes, the 45° -axis was the closest to one principal curvature direction, along which the strains underwent the largest change due to snap-through. After snapping, the strains on the top surface ($z=+H/2$) were all negative, since the top surface was being compressed when the force was applied. The strains on the bottom surface ($z=-H/2$) were all positive. These signs were consistent with the direction of the SMA-induced curvature change in fig. 2. Similar characteristics can be described for test 2, except snapping occurred at a temperature of 98.6° F,

5.40° F lower than test 1. Despite this 5.40° F difference, the average snapping temperature for the two tests was close to the predicted value.

Fig. 4. SMA wire temperature-laminate strain relations: [-30₄/30₄]_T

The predicted pre-snap-through strain levels were close to the measured values, and for a given gage location, the pre-snap-through strain levels for both tests were similar. For example, just prior to snap-through, the 45° gage on the top surface measured about -400με for both tests, and the prediction was about -450με. Just after snap-through, that same gage registered about -680με for both tests, and the theory predicted about -690με. Similar comparisons just before and just after snap-through can be made for most gages. As mentioned above, it was how the strains reached the pre-snap-through levels as a function of temperature that was not well predicted. With increasing temperature from the room-temperature start condition, the measured strains did not change much, then suddenly changed at the snap-through temperature. In contrast, after 82.4° F the prediction indicated the strains should have increased steadily until snap-through. It is believed much of this discrepancy was due to the lack of flexibility in the model. In the experiments, a considerable part of the laminate deformations due to the SMA forces could have taken place locally at the base of the support until the forces were large enough to cause snap-through. Then the overall deformation level changed suddenly. With the supports attached basically at a point, this could have easily been the

case. The model, on the other hand, was based on three curvature parameters, namely c_9 , c_{10} and c_{11} in eq. 4, that were assumed to be valid over the entire laminate, not just in the center, where the strain gages were mounted, nor just at the base of the supports, where the force was being transmitted into the laminate. It is also felt that the nylon insulators at the base of the supports and the nylon bolts for attaching the supports may have contributed to local flexibility of the support. Nylon is soft compared to the steel of the supports.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper explored the concept of using SMA wires to change the equilibrium configuration of unsymmetric laminates. An approximate theory has been presented to predict the snap-through of unsymmetric laminates induced by SMA wires. The laminate mechanical behavior was predicted by a theory based on assumed strain and displacement fields, the Rayleigh-ritz technique and virtual work. The equations governing the laminate behavior were coupled to equations governing the SMA wire behavior. The snap-through characteristics of the laminate were predicted as a function of the temperature in the SMA wire by solving the set of coupled equations. Experiments that were used to study SMA-induced deformations in four unsymmetric laminates were described. Laminate strain levels vs. temperature in the wire were measured for these laminates. The experimental results showed good repeatability and were in reasonable agreement with the predictions. From the results of this investigation, it is clear that it is possible to use SMA wires to change the shape of unsymmetric laminates and to predict quite well the laminate overall response as a function of the SMA wire temperature.

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